

Enhancing Epidural Training with Feedback

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Abstract. In this study, we set out to determine a smart training protocol for simulation-based epidural analgesia, using a haptic bimanual simulator we designed and assessed in previous work and exploiting motor learning theories. We trained healthcare students with personalized feedback to adopt desired strategies, and introduced motor variability by varying simulated patient weights. Our results confirmed the relationship between probing and velocity strategies and procedure outcome, found that personalized feedback improved probing movements but not velocity in the epidural space, and showed that motor variability did not affect performance. These insights contribute to refining simulation-based training and assessment approaches for novices in epidural analgesia.

Keywords: Medical simulation · Haptics · Skill Acquisition · Epidural Analgesia.

1 Introduction

Epidural analgesia is a widely used pain relief method, and its success depends heavily on the anesthesiologist's case experience. The task is believed to be very difficult to master, and requires extensive training, which might jeopardize patient safety. Hence, medical simulation has the potential to optimize skill acquisition in the task, while maintaining unharmed patient care.

Although some simulators for epidural analgesia have been developed in the past [1], none were bimanual or used smart training protocols, based on motor learning principles. Hence, our goal in this study was to determine a preferred training protocol for simulation-based skill acquisition in epidural analgesia. We addressed this aim by testing the added value of motor variability (which has the potential to increase learning rates [2]) by varying simulated patient weights, and proficiency-based-progression (PBP, in which trainees deliberately practice to improve their performance, measured using unambiguous metrics [3]). Our previous findings [4] indicated that participants probed with the loss-of-resistance (LOR) syringe more in successful trials compared to unsuccessful trials, and their velocity in the epidural space was decreased in successful trials. This helped us to determine desired values for the number of probing movements and velocity in the epidural space, which were used in this study for implementing PBP.

2 Methods

We used a haptic bimanual simulator that we designed and assessed in previous work [5] that emulates the forces applied on the task instruments throughout the procedure and

Fig. 1. Experimental design: (a) Group conditions, (b) Protocol details.

allows for patient weight variability and recording kinematic data. 40 healthcare students participated in this study and were divided into four groups (Fig 1(a), $N=10$ per group). The protocols are depicted in Fig 1(b): Participants began with an initial familiarization trial not included in data analysis, then completed 10 baseline trials at a patient weight of 71 kg. In the 54 training trials, the *Constant* groups practiced with the same 71 kg weight, while the *Variable* groups used six weights ranging from 55 to 130 kg. All participants underwent 5 test trials at 71 kg, followed by 15 generalization trials with new weights between 65 and 125 kg. There were four five-minute breaks throughout the experiment. From the second break onward, participants in the *PBP Feedback* groups received personalized feedback (in the form of PBP) about their performance, instructing them to increase the number of probing movements and decrease their velocity in the epidural space (until reaching the desired values).

We analyzed kinematic data, while focusing on the number of probing movements and velocity in the epidural space per trial. To solidify our assertion that these metrics are suited for evaluating performance indirectly, we examined them against trial outcome. To assess learning, we tested these metrics in the baseline trials ('BL') and compared them to the test and generalization trials ('END'), separately for each group. We used the Wilcoxon signed-rank test to test for statistical significance, and calculated non-parametric bootstrap 95% confidence intervals for the means of the metrics.

3 Results and Discussion

We found that participants probed more in successful trials compared to unsuccessful trials (Fig. 2(a), $p = 0.0052$), and that ES velocity was decreased in successful trials (Fig. 2(a), $p = 7.466 \cdot 10^{-7}$). These findings strengthen our conclusions from [4], and allow us to measure performance indirectly by using these metrics, which can be useful for objective level assessment.

Participants in the *PBP Feedback* groups probed more in the 'END', compared to 'BL' (Fig. 2(b), $p_{CF} = 0.002$, $p_{VF} = 0.002$). This demonstrates the advantage of simulation-based training, as measuring such unambiguous metrics and presenting them to the trainee is not possible in non-simulation-based training. The provision of feedback did not help in training participants to decrease ES velocity (Fig. 2(b)), which could be due to the mechanical difficulty of controlling velocity in a vacant space that

Fig. 2. (a) Probing movements and velocity in ES, in successful trials ('S') compared to trials that led to errors ('E'). (b) Probing movements and velocity in ES in baseline ('BL') compared to test and generalization ('END'), divided into groups. Colored bars represent the mean in the relevant groups and trials, the points represent each participant's value, and the black error bars represent 95% confidence intervals for the means. * : $p < 0.05$

is entered right after passing through a very rigid tissue [5]. In the *no PBP Feedback* groups, there was no difference between 'BL' and 'END' in either of the metrics.

The fact that motor variability did not affect skill acquisition is surprising, given the promise it is believed to hold in motor learning [2]. However, excluding motor variability in training can simplify the simulation and reduce the trainee's cognitive load.

Our conclusions will help us develop a training protocol for our next study, where we will train anesthesia residents and assess if our simulator improves real-life performance.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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